

An Integrative Review of the Genus *Onobrychis*: Biological Characteristics, Economic Importance, and Multilevel Taxonomic Tools

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Abstract

The genus *Onobrychis* is a plant genus comprising many important forage species cultivated in different regions of the world, particularly for their good forage quality, drought resistance, and contribution to sustainable agriculture. This review summarizes general information about the biological characteristics, economic importance, and taxonomic structure of the genus by combining different approaches. First, the growth conditions and phenology of *Onobrychis* species are discussed. Morphological characteristics commonly used to identify and separate species are examined, along with recent changes in the genus's classification and newly added species. Cytogenetic studies, such as chromosome number, karyotype analysis, and genome size differences, are presented to illustrate how they aid in understanding the relationships among species. The use of other tools, including DNA markers and phylogenetic analyses, is also described, particularly in addressing taxonomic problems where morphology alone is insufficient. Recent advances in genomic techniques are also discussed, as they provide more detailed information about genetic diversity and support more accurate taxonomic decisions. Overall, this review brings together information from morphology, cytogenetics, molecular biology, and genomics to provide an up-to-date overview of the genus *Onobrychis*. The aim is to provide a clear and useful overview for researchers studying this group and those interested in its agricultural and economic value.

Keywords: *Onobrychis*, Taxonomy, Morphology, Cytogenetics, Economic importance, Phenology

Introduction

Fabaceae (Leguminosea) forage crops are a group of plants of great importance worldwide in terms of the sustainability of animal production, the preservation of soil fertility, and the reduction of environmental impacts¹. These plants are essential components of agricultural systems due to their high protein content, their ability to enrich the soil through biological nitrogen fixation, and their adaptability to diverse ecological conditions. Therefore, the genus *Onobrychis* is an important forage crop genus due to its high forage quality, drought resistance, and soil-fertility enhancing properties¹. The genus has a wide geographical distribution and is scientifically significant due to its species diversity, morphological variability, and complex taxonomic structure. In recent years, many studies have been conducted to determine the relationships between *Onobrychis* species using classical morphological approaches as well as cytogenetic, molecular, and genomic methods. These developments have not only contributed to a clearer delineation of species boundaries but have also made it possible to more accurately assess the evolutionary history, genetic diversity, and agricultural potential of the genus. Therefore, bringing together information obtained at different levels necessitates a holistic approach to the genus.

This review aims to present the current literature on the characteristics, economic importance, and taxonomic approaches of the *Onobrychis* genus. By considering morphological, cytogenetic, molecular, and genomic data together, the goal is to contribute to a better understanding of the genus's systematic structure. Thus, the aim is to create a comprehensive and up-to-date reference source for both researchers working in this field and stakeholders interested in the genus from an agricultural and economic perspective.

Genus *Onobrychis*

Leguminosea or Fabaceae, which is among the flowering plant families in the world, is the third largest plant group with 19,400 species and about 730 genera are included in this group. The cultivation of the Fabaceae family, which has an important place in providing the energy, protein and minerals needed by humans and animals, dates back to ancient times¹. Therefore Fabaceae family is an economically and medically important plant family². Commonly known as the pea family, Fabaceae are generally characterized by compound leaves and the production of fruits known as legumes³. The Fabaceae family consists of subfamilies Papilionoideae, Mimosoideae and Caesalpinioideae found in temperate and tropical climates. Fabaceae are characterized with

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trees, shrubs, vines, or herbs, with stipulate, often compound leaves and typically pentamerous flowers, usually with a single, unicarpellous pistil with marginal placentation and the fruit a legume⁴. The leaves are usually compound, sometimes simple. Flowering is variable but typically bracteate. Flowers are usually bisexual, sometimes unisexual, actinomorphic, or zygomorphic, petiolate or sessile, hypogynous or periginous. The fruit is a legume, sometimes divided into non-separating, winged, drupelike or transverse segments⁴. Family members show great differences in terms of these characteristic features⁵. The roots of members of the Fabaceae family have a symbiotic relationship with nitrogen-fixing bacteria that induce the formation of root nodules. Beside have an important place in agriculture with their ability to make nitrogen in the air usable by plants, thanks to the symbiosis they perform with the help of *Rhizobium* bacteria¹.

The first information about the genus *Onobrychis* started when Linneus (1753) included the species belonging to the genus *Onobrychis* in the genus *Hedysarum* in his work called *Species Plantarum*⁶. Miller was the first person to name this genus by collecting *Onobrychis* species under the genus *Onobrychis*⁵. Then, many species and studies were carried out in the genus *Onobrychis* by different researchers⁶. Taxonomically, *Onobrychis* Miller is a genus in the Dicotyledonae (dicotyledons) class of Angiospermae (angiosperms) in the plant kingdom, and in the Papilionoidae subfamily of the Fabaceae (Leguminosae, Legume) family of the order Rosales. *Onobrychis* is a genus belonging to the family Fabaceae and the tribe *Hedysareae*, common in temperate regions of North America, Europe, and the Middle East⁷. *Onobrychis* is one of the most difficult genera in the Fabaceae family to diagnose and characterize⁸. In the literature, studies have been carried out on a small number of species, using a limited number of characters for the identification and separation of parts of the genus *Onobrychis*. Generally morphological and cytogenetic characters such as annual or perennial species, chromosome number and size, flower color, number of ovules, pod color, and flower and pod shape have been focused on for *Onobrychis* genus⁸. The *Onobrychis* family is a genus that has problems in collecting material. This difficulty is due to the fact that the flower color fades and changes during the herbarium formation of the genus, and the flowers and fruits fall off easily after drying⁶. In addition, the inadequacy of the species identification keys of the genus *Onobrychis* appears as another problem and causes differences in species studies⁵.

Taxonomically, *Onobrychis* is a critical genus. The taxonomy of *Onobrychis* is not completely determined, with contradictory schemes for its internal structure and species content⁹. This genus has high polymorphism in its morphological characters, so the boundaries of some taxonomic species are very clear. For this reason, many studies performed regarding its taxonomy based on morphological, cytological features and the compounds it contains. Researchers have suggested different classification according to fruit morphology, chromosome number and flower color. Furthermore several biosystematics studies ranging from non-molecular data to DNA sequences have been carried out on *Onobrychis* genus¹⁰. Şirjaev (1925) presented a classification for *Onobrychis*

his genus based on floral characteristics and the study is still accepted by many researchers. In that study, the genus consists of two subgenera, *Onobrychis* and *Sisyrosema*. Subgenus *Onobrychis* includes four sections *Dendrobrychis* DC, *Lophobrychis*, *Onobrychis*, and *Hemicyclobrychis* while the subgenus *Sisyrosema* comprises four sections *Anthyllium*, *Afghanicae*, *Heliobrychis*, *Hymenobrychis* (Table 1)¹¹. Rechinger (1984) reclassified the two subgenera into four and five sections, namely *Onobrychis*, *Dendrobrychis* DC., *Lophobrychis* Hand.-Mazz., *Laxiflorae* (Şirj.) Rech.f., *Anthyllium* Nábělek, *Afghanicae* Şirj., *Heliobrychis* Bunge ex Boiss., *Hymenobrychis* DC. and *Insignes* (Şirj.) Rech.f., respectively¹². Şirjaev (1925) divided the genus into two subgenera, *Onobrychis* as *EuOnobrychis* (Bunge ex Boiss.) Şirj. and *Sisyrosema* (Bunge ex Boiss.) Şirj. each with four sections based on floral characteristics. However, the sectional positions of *O. splendida* Rech.f. & Podlech and *O. freitagii* Rech.f. have remained hitherto uncertain¹⁰.

A karyological study found that unlike *Onobrychis* subgenus, *Sisyrosema* subgenus is monophyletic¹³. About with 30 species *Heliobrychis* is one of the richest parts of *Onobrychis* in terms of species, which includes perennial species found in Iran, Türkiye and Caucasia¹⁴. 21 *Onobrychis* species found in Iran are included in the *Sisyrosema* subgenus class¹⁵. The flowers of *Onobrychis* subgenus are commonly pink, rarely cream or white. The flowers of the *Sisyrosemae* subgenus are commonly yellow, rarely cream or white. *Onobrychis* genus has included perennial or annual members. The exact number of *Onobrychis* species is not known. The center of *Onobrychis* diversity is western Asia and the eastern Mediterranean regions, with about 130 species of this species mostly found in temperate regions¹⁶. According to the classification of *Onobrychis* developed by Şirjaev (1925), it is accepted that there were originally 126 species of this genus¹¹. The *Onobrychis* genus is represented throughout the world with 162 species and in Türkiye there are 52 species 60 taxon. 27 of these species found in Türkiye are endemic. *Onobrychis* is especially concentrated and diversified in the Anatolian-Iran-Caucasus triangle. In these regions, there are 53 species in Iran, 52 species in Türkiye and 39 species in the Caucasus⁵. There are also 62 species of *Onobrychis* in Russia, 17 species in Afghanistan, nine in Turkmenistan, nine in Tajikistan and 14 species in Iraq¹⁷. Approximately 173 species are existed by the International Legume Database and Information Service¹⁸. Yıldız et al. (1999) in study conducted according to fruit morphology, it was determined that there are 170 species, eight sections and two subgenera of *Onobrychis* genus⁸. Another study reported that *Onobrychis* Mill. genus *Hedysareae* (Fabaceae) is the second largest genus of the tribe and has more than 173 annual or perennial species^{19,20}. In another study, 342 perennial and annual species of *Onobrychis* were indicated²¹. In the Healthy Hay project, which is the European Union Legum Forage Crops Research Project, carried out in 2012, 362 different sainfoin species were identified across Europe²².

Economic importance of member of *Onobrychis* and sainfoin

Genus *Onobrychis* has a large number of species. Agriculturally important *Onobrychis* species are *O. viciifolia*

Table 1. Taxonomic classification of the genus *Onobrychis*¹⁰ rpl32/rpl32-trnL (UAG).

Širjaev (1925, 1926)	Boissier (1872)	Townsend (1974)	Rechinger (1984)	Aktoklu (1995)	Present study
Subgenus <i>EuOnobrychis</i> (Bunge ex Boiss.) Širj.	<i>EuOnobrychis</i> Bunge	Subgenus <i>Onobrychis</i>	Subgenus <i>Onobrychis</i>	Subgenus <i>Onobrychis</i>	Subgenus <i>Onobrychis</i>
Sect. <i>Eubrychis</i> DC. (including subsects. Macropterae Hand-Mazz., Macrosemiae Hand-Mazz., Brachysemiae Hand-Mazz., albae Hand-Mazz., Hispanicae Širj. and Vulgatæ Hand-Mazz.)		Sect. <i>Onobrychis</i>	Sect. <i>Onobrychis</i>	Sect. <i>Onobrychis</i>	Sect. <i>Onobrychis</i>
Sect. <i>Dendrobrychis</i> DC. (including sers. Dielsianae Širj. and Litvinovianae Širj.)		Sect. <i>Dendrobrychis</i> DC.	Sect. <i>Dendrobrychis</i> DC.	Sect. <i>Dendrobrychis</i> DC.	
Sect. <i>Lophobrychis</i> Hand-Mazz. (including subsects. Occidentales Širj. and Orientales Širj.)		Sect. <i>Lophobrychis</i> Hand-Mazz.	Sect. <i>Lophobrychis</i> Hand-Mazz.	Sect. <i>Lophobrychis</i> Hand-Mazz.	
Sect. <i>Hemicyclobrychis</i> Širj.					Sect. <i>Hemicyclobrychis</i> Širj.
Subgenus <i>Sisyrosema</i> (Bunge ex Boiss.) Širj.	<i>Sisyrosema</i> Bunge	Subgenus <i>Sisyrosema</i> (Bunge ex Boiss.) Širj.	Subgenus <i>Sisyrosema</i> (Bunge) Grossha	Subgenus <i>Sisyrosema</i> (Bunge) Grossha	Subgenus <i>Sisyrosema</i> (Bunge ex Boiss.) Širj.
Sect. <i>Afghanicae</i> Širj.		Sect. <i>Anthyllium</i> Nábëlek	Sect. <i>Afghanicae</i> Širj.	Sect. <i>Hellobrychis</i>	Sect. <i>Afghanicae</i> Širj.
Sect. <i>Anthyllium</i> Nábëlek (including subsects. Fedtschenkoonae Širj., Lipskyanae Širj., Mirae Širj. and Nábëlekianae Širj.)		Sect. <i>Anthyllium</i> Nábëlek	Sect. <i>Anthyllium</i> Nábëlek	Sect. <i>Hymenobrychis</i>	
					Sect. Lipskyanae (Širj.) Amiran. & Kaz. Osaloo
Sect. <i>Hellobrychis</i> Bunge (including subsects. Szovitsianae Širj., Boissierianae Širj. and Persicae Širj.)		Sect. <i>Hellobrychis</i> (Bunge ex Boiss.) Širj.	Sect. <i>Hellobrychis</i> Bunge ex Boiss.		Sect. <i>Hellobrychis</i> (Bunge ex Boiss.) Širj.
Sect. <i>Hymenobrychis</i> DC. (including subsects. <i>Insignes</i> Širj., <i>Modestae</i> Širj., <i>Pulcherrimae</i> Širj. and <i>Laxiflorae</i> Širj.)		Sect. <i>Hymenobrychis</i> DC.	Sect. <i>Hymenobrychis</i> DC.		Sect. <i>Hymenobrychis</i> DC.
			Sect. <i>Insignes</i> (Širj.) Rech.f.		Sect. <i>Insignes</i> (Širj.) Rech.f.
					Sect. <i>Laxiflorae</i> (Širj.) Rech.f.
					Sect. Litvinovianae (Širj.) Amiran. & Kaz. Osaloo

**DC. : De Candolle, Hand-Mazz. : Handel-Mazzetti, Širj. : Širjaev, Boiss. : Boissier, Rech.f. : Rechinger Filius, Rech. : Rechinger, Grossh. : Grossheim, Subg.: Subgenus, Sect.: Section, Subsect.: Subsection, Ser. : Series, Incl.:including

(Common Sainfoin), *O. arenaria* (Anatolian Sainfoin), *O. transcaucasica* (Caucasian Sainfoin), *O. montana* D.C., *O. sativa* var. *persica* (Şirjaev pro var.)²³. Among these species, *O. viciifolia*, which is called common sainfoin and is widely cultivated around the world²⁴. *Onobrychis* is an important forage legume crop with perennial and annual growing habit⁷.

The history of sainfoin as a forage extends for centuries in Europe and the Middle East, with reports of its use as early as the 1500s. The initial reported scientific trials about sainfoin in the UK were conducted as early as 1668²⁵. Sainfoin was widely grown in Euroasia before the widespread use of commercial fertilizers⁷ and production spread to North America in the 19th and 20th centuries. It is a very tasty and nutritious legume fodder plant that produces hay and pasture²⁶. Studies show that sainfoin has anthelmintic properties, methane control potential from ruminants, and protein protection ability against premature deterioration in the rumen when used as a fodder in the diet of ruminants owing to the tannin compound it contains²⁷. The plant is resistant to drought, cold and low nutrient availability but is not resistant to high soil salinity and high water tables²⁶. Sainfoin is an important component in sustainable agriculture due to the ability to convert atmospheric nitrogen into bioavailable compounds, which reduce the dependency to regular input of inorganic nitrogen⁹.

The genus *Onobrychis*, which grows naturally in Anatolia, consists of two subgenera, *Onobrychis* and *Sisyroserma*. *Onobrychis* subgenus divided into 3 different sections as *Dendrobrychis*, *Laphobrychis* and *Onobrychis*⁵. Approximately 70 *Onobrychis* species naturally grow in Türkiye as the country is situated on the natural distribution range of the genus and is one of the centers of genetic diversity²⁸. Sainfoin is also known as görüngen or korunga in Türkiye²⁹. Sainfoin is defined as the king of forage crops in Türkiye due to its superior agricultural characteristics, high yield and quality feed that can adapt to different ecological regions of Türkiye³⁰. Sainfoin has a large cultivation area, especially in the Eastern provinces of our country, and also found in many places in Central Anatolia²⁹. Unlike alfalfa and some other legumes, sainfoin does not cause bloat in animals owing to the concentrated tannins³¹.

Since 1990, the production of sainfoin has an increasing momentum in Türkiye. According to TÜİK data, sainfoin cultivation area has fluctuated in recent years. Sainfoin cultivation area increased from 957,590 hectares in 1990 to 1,792,534 hectares in 2020 and 1,814,737 hectares in 2021³². However, it decreased in subsequent years, reaching 1,241,541 hectares in 2024. Similarly, sainfoin's green forage production was determined to be 1,781,789 tons in 2020 and 1,468,830 tons in 2024³³. Because of the high amount of nectar it contains, the sainfoin functions as a good bee pasture. It is seen that high yield and honey quality are obtained from beehives in areas where sainfoin is cultivated²⁹.

Growth conditions and phenology

The growth stage of the sainfoin is defined as follows: seedling emerge (Em), vegetative stage - no stem elongation (V1), vegetative stage - stem elongation (E1), early bud: 1 to 2 nodes with buds; no flowers or seed

pods (B1), late bud: > 2 nodes with buds; no flowers or seed pods (B2), early flowering: one node with one open flower; no seed pods (F1), peak/late flowering: >= 2 nodes with open flower; no seed pods (F2), early seed pod: 1 to 3 nodes with green seed pods (P1), late seed pod: > 3 nodes with green seed pods (P2), ripe seed pod: nodes with mostly brown mature seed pods (P3), postharvest: after harvesting all seeds, fruit, or forage (PH1), dormant winter period (DO)³⁴.

Onobrychis species, which are highly resistant to drought and cold, can also be cultivated in barren and calcareous areas where other crop species cannot be cultivated as it is adapted to high temperature, rainfall, drought, salinity, diseases and pests^{35,36}. *Onobrychis* can be planted in spring in areas with harsh winters, and in autumn in regions with mild winters¹.

Sainfoin has many hollow stems which arise from basal buds to form a branched crown⁹. Pink, white, yellow or purple flowers of *Onobrychis* are highly attractive to pollinators. Sainfoin is an allagomous plant, and the female organ is longer than male organ. Sainfoin is generally cross-pollinated, mostly by honey bees (*Apis mellifera* L.) and leaf cutting bees (*Megachile rotundata* Fabricius.)⁷. In addition, bumble bees (*Bombus* spp.) are also frequent visitors to sainfoin fields. *Bombus* spp. generally visit the sainfoin between morning and noon because there is not much wind, and flowers are ready for pollinators. Pollination success is relatively high in sainfoin. The duration between the opening of the first flower and the withering of the terminal flowers on a raceme is about 2-3 weeks. Sainfoin produces single-seeded indehiscent brown colored pods. Seed color varies from olive to brown or black. The seeds are kidney-shaped, with a smooth surface³⁷. *Onobrychis* species have a deep taproot and in addition to this taproot, it has thick and many thin roots that come out sideways. The length of this pile root can reach 1-10 m depths, depending on the soil and climatic conditions where the sainfoin grows. Thanks to its deep roots, it aerates the soil and uses the nutrients and water from the depths²⁸. There are less minerals such as calcium and sodium in sainfoin compared to other legumes. However, it has been determined that it is rich in phosphorus, magnesium and potassium^{38,39}.

Fruit set depends upon the species and variety, but it can be correlated with the suitability and adaptability of its environment. The flowers open gradually over 24-h especially between night and sunrise^{23,40,41}.

Morphology

The genus *Onobrychis* consists of annual or perennial (most of the species are perennial) herbaceous species and a small number of spiny-radius species. The stem, which is ligneous or buttress in the lower parts, can be hairy or hairless. The stipules, which can be seen as free or compound, are usually membranous and have hairy edges. The leaflets are whole-edged, round to oblong in shape, and the apex ends with a hard tip. The leaflets are attached to the leaf axis at the base by a long stalk, and at the upper parts by a short stalk, and are rarely sessile. The inflorescence is axial and panicle. The calyx is bell-shaped, the teeth are unequal and usually lanceolate. Petals of flower can be yellow, pink, white,

cream or mauve and have dark veins. Flag leaf has an elliptic structure and in some species the back is hairy. The paddles are generally shorter than the sepals, with auriculars and scapus. The boat is shorter than or equal to the flag leaf. The ovary has 1-3 ovules. Male organs are in diadelphous structure. The fruit is nearly round, does not open when dry and contains 1-2 seeds. It is soft hairy or hairless. Seeds are kidney or oblong shaped⁵.

Onobrychis is closely related to *Hedysarum*, but the fruit always consists of only one segment and the ovary has 1-2 egg cell, and the crown of *Onobrychis* species is standard and shorter than the tip⁴². Hedge (1970) defined the characteristic features of sections of subgenera as follows: Characteristics of *Onobrychis* subgenera, *Dendrobrychis* section: plant semi-bush, spiny, perennial⁴². Characteristics of *Onobrychis* subgenera, *Lophobrychis* section: annual herbaceous. *Onobrychis* subgenera, *Onobrychis* section, characteristic features are perennial herbs, fruit has no distinct junction and stem. Characteristics of section *Sisyrosema* subgenera, *Heliobrychis*: rarely annual, usually perennial herbs. Characteristics of the section *Sisyrosema* subgenera, *Hymenobrychis*: herbaceous perennials⁴².

Sainfoin (*Onobrychis viciifolia*) axillary tillers possess inflorescences in an erect raceme, which contains approximately 70-80 flowers. The flowers have a pleasant scent. The sainfoin fruit is a semicircular, small flat pod with a single seed. The fruit pericarp surrounds the seed. The pericarps of the fruits are net-shaped, veined and form a protrusion on the semicircular edges³⁹. The top of the fruit is veined in the form of a net and the semicircular edge is thorny in the form of a protrusion²⁸. Fruit structure consists of bristly hairy or glabrous, rarely fine soft hairy, woolly or coarse hairy structure, two rows in the middle, honeycomb-like surface disc and margins of varying width⁵. Sainfoin is a deep-rooted perennial legume with erect or sub-erect hollow stems growing up to a height of 100 cm. It has a deep tap root system with few main branches and numerous fine lateral roots, which provide sites for root nodule development. Leaves are pinnately compounded with 5-14 pairs of leaflets and a terminal leaflet³⁷. It can be approximately 100-120 cm in length, its surface is slightly hairy and there are 5-30 leaflets on its leaves. These, too, have a flat structure with a length of about 10-25 mm and a width of 3-8 mm³⁹. Sainfoin has many hollow stems which arise from basal buds to form a branched crown⁹. Pink, white, yellow or purple flowers of sainfoin are highly attractive to pollinators²⁷.

Fruit morphology in the genus *Onobrychis* varies significantly among sections. According to Yildiz et al. (1999), in section *Dendrobrychis*, the fruit is single-segmented, sessile, and generally spineless, though spiny varieties are rarely observed. The fruit, lacking any differentiation between dorsal and ventral surfaces, exhibits a symmetrical structure and bears a single seed (uniovulate) in the ovary. In section *Heliobrychis*, the fruit consists of a single disc with no apex. The fruits are curved and petiolate (stipitate), with a smooth stem and stiff hairs (setae) on the edges. Large, deep faveoles are arranged irregularly or in three or four rows on the fruit surface. The largest faveole is located apically and is usually spiny. The fruits of this section are densely hairy⁸. In section *Hyme-*

nobrychis, the fruit is curved, broad-apposed, and often toothed or spiny. Deeply, large faveoles are arranged in two rows at the apex and on the disc, with linear to rectangular faveoles located at the apex. In this section, which usually contains two ovules, the ventral suture is fully curved, and the fruit tips are fused⁸. In Section *Lophobrychis*, the fruit is asymmetrical, with a toothed apex and two or three rows of deep, large faveoles on the disc. The fruits are sessile and often spiny. In Section *Onobrychis*, the fruit is sessile, erect, or slightly curved, and bears spiny or toothed crests on the disc and apex. There are no faveoles at the apex, while the disc has two regular rows of deep faveoles. The terminal faveole is longer than the others and generally spineless. The fruit is single-ovulated and has enlarged spines on its edges⁸. Zarrabian et al. grouped fruit types according to their morphological characteristics. Type 1 fruits are typical of *Onobrychis* section and are small, round, and slightly wrinkled; the oval to spherical seeds show no significant textural variation. Type 2 fruits, typical of *Sisyrosema* section, are characterized by long, cylindrical, and smooth pods; the seeds are more angular, smooth, and generally larger. Type 3 fruits, typical of *Lophobrychis* section, have flat, prominently ridged pods; the seeds are large, irregularly shaped, and have distinct surface textures. The recently described *O. crista-galli* type fruits are distinguished by long, curved pods bearing ridges or spines; the seeds are large and have a rough surface⁴³. Another study on *Onobrychis* fruit morphology reported that most species are reniform, single-seeded, and characterized by lateral curvature. Some species exhibit round or slightly oval fruit shapes, while the edges may have spiny or wavy structures. Fruit surfaces may be completely smooth and flat, or they may be covered with fine hairs. Additionally, some species exhibit prominent veins or bubble-like structures on the fruit surface⁴⁴.

Cytogenetics

Cytological markers are variations in chromosome numbers, band patterns, sizes, shapes, order, and positions. These variations reveal differences in euchromatin and heterochromatin distributions and can also be used in the identification of linkage groups and in physical mapping⁴⁵.

Most cytological studies in the *Onobrychis* genus have focused on chromosome number and length. *Onobrychis* species have basic chromosome number of $x=7$, $x=8$ and in the genus $2n=2x=14$, $2n=4x=28$, $2n=2x=16$, $2n=4x=32$ different chromosome numbers have been reported⁴⁶. The *Onobrychis* genus has included diploid, tetraploid or octaploid forms but generally *Onobrychis* is diploid or tetraploid. While tetraploid species may be autopolyploid or allopolyploid, it is unclear whether the inheritance is tetrasomic or disomic²³. This change in chromosome number has been thought to be the cause of the evolutionary change in *Onobrychis*. According to some researchers, $x=8$ is the ancestral chromosome number of the genus *Onobrychis*, and with aneuploidy, species with the basic chromosome number $x=7$ emerged, but according to some researchers, the evolution and change in the genus changed the basic chromosome number from $x=7$ to $x=8$ is thought to increase⁴⁷. The genus *Onobrychis* has chromosomes ranging in len-

ght from 1.6 μm to 2.6 μm and in metacentric, submetacentric form ⁴⁶.

O. viciifolia has seven basic chromosomes and includes both diploid and tetraploid varieties. *O. viciifolia* has an average length of 3.39 μm of chromosomes ⁴⁸. The scarcity of chromosome markers in *Onobrychis*, which complicates karyotype analysis, poses a problem. To overcome this problem, karyotypes were produced for comparative analysis by examining the chromosome number and the evolution of ribosomal DNA (rDNA) loci in 29 *Onobrychis* species. As a result of the analysis, two different basic chromosome numbers, $x=7$ and $x=8$, emerged in diploid and tetraploid species. In addition, it was determined that diploid *Onobrychis* species showed a high polymorphism in the number and localization of rDNA loci, and similar rDNA loci were present in polyploids. Chromosomal pattern analysis of rRNA loci in a phylogenetic context resulted in the restructuring of an ancestral 5S rDNA locus and a 35S rDNA locus in the interstitial chromosomal position within the genus, inferring that the ancestral chromosome number was $x=8$, and the presence of diminished dysploidy and polyploidization as the main mechanisms of chromosome number evolution ⁴⁹.

Although the sainfoin is important from an agricultural point of view, its basic chromosome and centromere features have not been defined yet. Therefore, in order to determine the phylogenetic relationship between species in sainfoin, there is a need to analyze the centromeric histone CENH3 by performing genome and centromere analysis. In this study, four different CENH3 alleles were discovered in the sainfoin genome. The allelic diversity of OvCENH3s discovered in the sainfoin supports an allotetraploid origin that has not been clarified in the sainfoin ⁵⁰.

Recent additions of species

The genus *Onobrychis* has a significant species richness as that is cross pollinated. However, it is a genus that is very difficult to define and determine species ⁶. New species in *Onobrychis* have been determined according to such as characters: annual or perennial nature of the species, adnate or free stipules, ovule number; size, proportions, and indumentum of floral parts; and some morphological characters of the fruit (such as seed number, pubescence, with or without setae and spines, presence or absence of crest, stalked or stalkless fruit, and curvature of stalk). However, a limited number of characters are used in new species identification studies ⁸.

Taxonomic relationship determined and defined of *Onobrychis* species found in the northwest Alborz Mountain range in Iran with other species that is aimed. *O. alamutensis* has been determined that has different characteristics compared to other species and is a new species. *O. alamutensis*, *O. verae*, *O. ptychophylla* and *O. sosnowskyi* were found to be more closely related to long-winged species. The morphological features of *O. alamutensis* were described as a dorsoventrally flattened capsule, invertebrate disc, short toothed apex of 0.2-0.5 mm, and long wings 11 mm long ⁵¹.

Compared with Flora of Turkiye, Flora of URSS, Flora of Iranica, Flora of Iraq, Flora of Palaestina, and some ge-

neral references, plant samples collected from Kars and Malatya were found to be two new species belonging to the genus *Onobrychis*. The sample collected from Malatya was named *Onobrychis fallax* Freyn & Sint. var. *longifolia* Aktoklu var. nova (Sect. *Onobrychis*), and the sample collected from Kars was named *Onobrychis atropatana* Boiss. var. *grandiflora* Aktoklu var. nova (Sect. *Heliobrychis*) ⁵.

Use of morphological traits in the taxonomy of genus

Morphological traits such as the presence and durability of sepals, fruit and seed size, shape, flower color, dorsal and abdominal ornamentation, wall thickness, pod opening, legume seed number play an important role in identifying species and revealing taxonomic relationships in *Onobrychis* genus and are frequently studied in studies ⁵². Morphological traits, particularly those pertaining to the flowers, are the main diagnostic characters used to distinguish species. However, morphological traits have some advantages and disadvantages. So, the variability of these characters does not always allow a clear distinction to be made ⁵³. Although these traits are relatively easy to examine, the effect of location, climate and environment, being exposed to epistatic or pleiotropic effects on their formation reduces the reliability of the results. In addition, since *Onobrychis* is a cross-pollinated plant, it varies a lot in terms of morphological traits ⁵⁴.

In the classification study performed on 77 species according to pollen morphology, 7 species *Dendrobrychis*, 5 species *Lophobrychis*, 14 species *Onobrychis*, 3 species *Laxiflorae*, 7 species *Anthyllum*, 3 species *Afghanicae*, 3 species *Insignes*, 21 species *Heliobrychis*, and 12 species *Hymenobrychis* with two unknown species determined to be included in the class ¹². In the study on pollen morphology in Iranian *Onobrychis* samples, it was concluded that the pollen morphology was homogeneous and that the pollen morphology could be defined by three pollen subtypes in terms of features such as pollen size, shape and ornamentation. It was concluded that there are some differences between these pollen subspecies, but these differences do not cause any change in the classification of the species ¹⁶. Pollen size and morphology of 20 *Onobrychis* taxa found in Turkiye were investigated using both light and scanning electron microscopy. In *Onobrychis*, there is a correlation between ploidy level or chromosome number and pollen size at the taxon level; An increase in pollen grain size was found in species with higher ploidy levels ⁵⁵. In order to determine the level of difference between 5 different sainfoin species examined in *Heliobrychis* section, 27 morphological characters were examined, and variation was detected between species in terms of morphological characters. The reason for these variations is thought to be the high rate of cross-pollinated of these species and their growing in different ecological conditions ⁵⁴. The taxonomic evaluation of 44 populations of 36 *Onobrychis* taxa belonging to two subspecies and six divisions according to their pollen morphology was made by electron and light microscopy. Prolate (dominant), perprolate and subprolate classes were determined according to the polar/equatorial axis length ratio. It has been observed that while the pollen grains differ according to the taxa in the equatorial view, the contour

shapes in the polar view are almost the same for all taxa. Three types of exines were found in the studied species: reticulated, supracreticula and micro-netted. The obtained results revealed that the palynological features of the genus are relatively homogeneous and have limited taxonomic importance⁵⁶. The genetic diversity between and within species was evaluated by evaluating the fruit, seed coat and seed storage protein counts of *O. arenaria*, *O. montana*, *O. viciifolia*, *O. alba*, *O. supina* and *O. caput-galli*. It was determined that other species showed similarity in terms of fruit morphometric characteristics, but the length, width, thickness and number of spines of the fruit of *O. caput-galli* were higher than those of other species. The highest values of seed coat thickness were recorded in diploid species and seed coats were determined to be highly variable. As a result of the evaluations made by electrophoretic analysis, it has been determined that the number and location of storage proteins vary between and within species⁵³. In the study carried out to determine the species belonging to the genus *Onobrychis*, which grows naturally in Erzurum and its environs in Turkey, and to determine the general prevalence, morphological and quality characteristics, species samples were collected from different locations during the flowering periods of 2007, 2008 and 2009. At the end of the study, a total of ten taxa representing eight species and two subspecies genotype was found. As a result of morphological evaluations, *O. atropatana* has the highest number of leaflets grandiflora, leaflet length and width are highest in *O. radiata*, number of main branches in *O. hajastana* has found. Furthermore raw ash ratio is highest in *O. stenostachya*, ADF and NDF ratio highest in *O. cornuta* and crude protein content in *O. stenostachya* has found⁵⁷.

Use of cytogenetic tools in the taxonomy of genus

Most of the earlier cytological studies in the genus are on the chromosome number⁵⁸. Chromosome number, chromosome structure, size and behavior are the most widely used cytological characters. Chromosome structure and behavior in meiosis have important implications in explaining the degree of relatedness among populations and their evolution. In a karyological study within the *Onobrychis* clade, the subgenus *Sisyrosema* was found to be monophyletic, unlike the *Onobrychis* subgenus¹³. Previous nrDNA ITS-based in a study for phylogenetic purposes showed that the *Onobrychis* subgenus was not monophyletic, while the *Sisyrosema* subgenus were monophyletic⁵⁹. Another study suggested that neither of these two subgenera were monophyletic¹⁰.

The morphological characters and meiotic chromosome numbers of *O. viciifolia*, *O. transcaucasica* and *O. altissima* populations in Iran were determined. It was stated that all taxa in the study had seven basic chromosome numbers and exhibited regular bivalent mating and chromosome separation in meiosis. In the study, it was determined that *O. viciifolia* and *O. altissima* were tetraploid ($2n=4x=28$), while *O. transcaucasica* was diploid ($2n=2x=14$). It was also determined that although *O. transcaucasica* is diploid, it has similar morphology with the tetraploid *O. transcaucasica* and *O. altissima* species⁵⁸. Chromosome numbers and morphological characteristics of *O. caput-galli*, *O. fallax*, *O. cappado-*

cica, *O. aequidentata*, *O. lasiostachya*, *O. viciifolia*, *O. oxyodonta*, *O. hypargyrea* species were determined by karyological techniques. In the study, it was determined that *O. cappadocica* $2n=16$, *O. viciifolia* $2n=28$ and the other species $2n=14$ and the karyotypes consisted of submedian-centromeric (sm) chromosomes in *O. oxyodonta* and median-centromeric (m) chromosomes in other species⁶⁰.

In the cytological characterisation study on *O. viciifolia* varieties and related species, the 2C value of sainfoin was determined to be approximately 2.5 pg. *O. viciifolia* each chromosome length $<5 \mu\text{m}$ and diploid ($2n=2x=14$) and tetraploid ($2n=4x=28$) varieties, *O. aequidentata* and *O. crista-galli*. The basic chromosome numbers were determined to be eight⁴⁸.

Use of molecular tools in the taxonomy of genus

A considerable amount of work has been performed for taxonomic evaluation and delineating of genetic diversity in the genus *Onobrychis*. Molecular markers are polymorphisms that exist between the nucleotide sequences of different individuals. Insertion, deletion, point mutations, duplication and translocation are the basis of these polymorphisms. An ideal DNA marker type should be co-dominant, evenly distributed throughout the genome, highly reproducible, and capable of detecting higher levels of polymorphism⁴⁵. Many marker systems employed in the genus *Onobrychis* up until now.

The nuclear internally transcribed spacer region of the chloroplast genome and DNA sequences for the trnH-psbA and trnT-trnL intergenic spacers among *Onobrychis* species showed significant genetic diversity between *O. viciifolia* and other *Onobrychis* species with. Furthermore, a genetic distinction is defined between *O. viciifolia* accessions from western Europe and those from eastern Europe and Asia, reflecting a similar division based on agronomic properties⁹. Genetic diversity characterization was performed among a panel of genotypes that included a total of 29 *O. viciifolia*, 40 other accessions from sect. *Onobrychis*, seven from sect. *Hymenobrychis* DC., six from sect. *Lophobrychis*, and two from sect. *Heliobrychis* Bunge ex Boiss. DNA sequences were obtained for the nuclear internal transcribed spacer region and the trnH-psbA and trnT-trnL intergenic spacers of the chloroplast genome revealed that there was a clear distinction between *Heliobrychis* and *Hymenobrychis*, and similarities between *Lophobrychis* and *Onobrychis* were evident⁹. In the cytological characterisation study on *O. viciifolia* varieties and related species, the 2C value of sainfoin was determined to be approximately 2.5 pg. with each chromosome length $<5 \mu\text{m}$ and diploids having $2n=2x=14$ and tetraploids having $2n=4x=28$ chromosomes. *O. aequidentata* and *O. crista-galli* were reported to have the basic chromosome numbers of eight⁴⁸.

Use of genomic tools in the taxonomy of genus

Genomic studies on sainfoin are very few in contrast to other forage crops such as alfalfa⁶¹. Researchers generally prefer polymerase chain reaction (PCR) based markers in their studies. These methods are Cleaved Amplified Polymorphic Sequence (CAPS), Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP), Simple Sequence Repeats

(SSR), Inter Simple Sequence Repeats (ISSR), Sequence Characterized Amplified Region (SCAR), Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD) and Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) ⁶². RAPD, AFLP, SSR and ISSR have recently been used in genomic studies to determine population structure, taxonomic relationship and genetic diversity in sainfoin ⁶¹.

The intensity of population genomic studies on the genus *Onobrychis* has lagged behind other cultivated plants with high economic values. The first reason for this situation can be attributed to the fact that the number of researchers working on the *Onobrychis* genus is much less than other crops and the low interest of private companies in crops that do not need to be planted every year. Another reason is the scarcity of early genomics tools available for population genomic studies. Many molecular applications have restricted its use in population genomic studies, where the discovery and use of a dense and robust set of genetic markers in many individuals is required. Ideally, population genomic studies should be conducted with molecular tools that allow large numbers (hundreds to thousands) of polymorphic markers to adequately cover the entire genome in a single experiment. Because of polyploidy, obligatory cross-pollination, and large genome sizes, marker discovery and technical development in *Onobrychis* use to be very costly ⁶¹. The first boring, unsound, and low-yield marker systems such as RFLP, AFLP, and RAPD were quickly replaced by more abundant and robust markers on the clover. As marker technology evolved towards low-cost and highly abundant SNP markers, high-resolution melting (HRM) technology based on transcriptome sequencing, and finally GBS-based SNPs were used in alfalfa genome mapping. These new and efficient population genomic tools are being used in alfalfa population genomic studies to understand patterns of genetic diversity, population structure, and association mapping ⁶¹.

Genetic diversity was determined in 80 sainfoin accessions using anatomical, morphological and molecular (by ISSR analysis) markers. As a result of the morphological evaluation were divided into three different groups that can be easily identified by features such as palatability, resistance to powdery mildew, and percentage of plant shoot and leaf. For anatomic features variation was found especially vessel diameter, sieve diameter, phloem width and xylem/phloem ratio. In the study, genetic diversity assessment was performed using 45 ISSR primers. As a result, it was concluded that the majority of genetic diversity is between accessions, there is less variation between geographic groups, and Asia and Eastern Europe may be the main diversity centers for this species ⁶³. RAPD markers and genetic diversity of 36 *O. sativa* populations cultivated in Iran were investigated. It was determined that 79 bands out of 5 of the 20 RAPD primers in the study were polymorphic and because of RAPD primer analysis, the genetic diversity value (uh) of 36 populations varied between 0.08 and 0.43, and the mean uh value was 0.25. Genetic diversity with analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) showed greater variability of 78% in populations. In addition, in the study, it was determined that the populations were divided into 3 groups according to the phylogenetic analysis ⁶⁴. In the study in which the Azerbaijani and Iranian sainfoin

populations were analyzed using ISSR markers, it was determined that the rate of polymorphic ISSR loci was between 38.75% and 61.25% among the populations, and the neutral genetic diversity value of Nei varied between 0.118 and 1.179 as a result of ISSR analysis ⁶⁵. In another study, a total of 68 alleles were identified in 91 samples to determine the genetic diversity of two *O. viciifolia* cultivars (Özerbey and Lütfübey) and three local populations in Türkiye (Pleven, Kırşehir-1 and Kırşehir-2) using 10 nSSR loci specially designed for *Onobrychis* species. It was reported that a high level of genetic diversity was observed at the rate of %92 within the population and %8 between the populations. According to the UPGMA dendrogram obtained as a result of the study, it was determined that the samples were divided into 2 groups: Özerbey and Lütfübey were in one group, and Pleven and Kırşehir-2 were in the second group ⁶⁶. In the study in which the diversity of 83 sainfoin genotypes determined according to their agronomic performances was evaluated, ten nuclear simple sequence repeat (nSSR) primers were used, and it was concluded that all nSSR loci were polymorphic, and a total of 92 alleles were detected and the average allele number observed for each locus was determined as 9.2. In the study, Shannon Index $I = 0.375$, unbiased genetic diversity value $u_h = 0.243$, and mean polymorphic information content $PIC = 0.240$. According to the data obtained from the studied sainfoin genotypes, it was concluded that they were divided into 2 main groups in the UPGMA clustering method analysis and into 3 main groups in the STRUCTURE analysis ⁶⁷.

Conclusion and future perspectives

The genus *Onobrychis* represents a group of plants that are valuable for sustainable agriculture and high-quality forage production yet have not yet been comprehensively and widely evaluated. This review combines findings from morphology, cytogenetics, molecular biology, and emerging genomic tools and highlights how multilevel approaches can clarify long-standing taxonomic uncertainties.

Given the progress in the research on the genus and advancement of the genomic and phenomic tools, several research venues could be suggested to further unveil the genus. Given the variation in the ploidy levels of the taxa included in the genus, a set of highly conserved ploidy independent genomic tools such as chloroplast and mitochondrial genome-based SNP markers can help to understand the status of and relationship among taxa. Moreover, broader germplasm sampling while employing such markers would also be an interesting research venue. The use image based phenomic approaches can more accurately define quantitative traits in the taxa and help identify species boundaries. Combination of genomic and phenomic tools would be another interesting research topic to follow.

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